

Thoth's Constant

π , φ , and e.

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Abstract

Divine

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1 Introduction

Just to formally introduce a ratio used previously, and give it a symbol.

I need it for upcoming documents, which links the great pyramid to the speed of light more accurately than any other extant method, and for deciphering the King's Chamber.

2 Symbols and values

Table 1 shows the usual irrationals. Construction is a practical art, so we need to use practical values for certain irrationals. It appears that while they used 3.1416 as π when needed, they were happy to approximate that to simpler versions like 3.14 or 3.142 when showing intent rather than exactitude was sufficient. Even today, we still use $22/7$ or 3.14 in school.

Equations shown below use a science/engineering approach, not pure mathematics, so $1.999 = 2.0$.

We should remember that we are dealing with a different culture, which may have had a different approach to accuracy and precision, compared to our modern scientific mindset. My Giza analysis suggests they typically worked to 3 or 4 decimal places. This may indicate that they used abacuses or counting tables,

Symbol	Name	"Full" value	Practical value	Practical % Accuracy
π	Archimedes' constant	3.141592653...	3.1416 or 3.142 or 3.14	99.9998, 99.9870 or 99.9493
e	Euler's number	2.718281828...	2.7183 or 2.718 or 2.72	99.9993 or 99.9896 or 99.9368
ϕ	Golden ratio	1.6180339887...	1.618 $\phi + 1 = \phi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
ρ	Plastic ratio	1.3247179572...	1.3247 or 1.325 $\rho + 1 = \rho^3 = 2.3247$	99.9986 or 9.9458
\mathcal{C}	Royal cubit	0.5236 m		

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

or possibly slide rules or logarithms, to calculate. Alternatively, they may just have used four decimals as anything more did not make sense in construction. 0.0001 \mathcal{C} is 0.05236 mm, which is about 50 microns, half the smallest distance that can be seen with the naked eye, and approaching the length of a human liver cell.

I use "cubit" for the Royal cubit (\mathcal{C}). Other researchers use other values, but 0.5236 works for me.

3 Thoth's Constant

Thoth's Constant, symbol ϑ , as defined as

$$\vartheta = \frac{\pi\phi}{e}$$

Wolfram Alpha (<https://www.wolframalpha.com/input?i=\pi\phi/e>) computes that as

1.87000613368955001896323177216265845824996304372...

Which rounds very nicely to a practical value of 1.87.

A culture without access to digital computers may instead have calculated it as

$$\vartheta = \frac{3.1416 \times 1.618}{2.7183} = 1.8699587242...$$

or, using 3 digits,

$$\vartheta = \frac{3.142 \times 1.618}{2.718} = 1.87040323767476...$$

Both of these results still round to 1.87.

4 The symbol

The symbol, ϑ , the script form of θ at Unicode point U+03D1, was chosen because

1. The Greek letter has the "th" sound.
2. This version of theta does not seem to be used much elsewhere in mathematics and science.

5 Use at Giza

My first encounter with 1.87 was when dissecting the cubit (The Beautiful Cubit System [1], The Beautiful System [2]). There are 28 digits in the royal cubit. The \mathcal{C} is 52.36cm, so

$$\text{digit} = \frac{52.36}{28} = 1.87 \text{ cm.}$$

The second time 1.87 appears is in *Khufu's Coffin* [3]. The width appears to be intended to be 1.87 \mathcal{C} , and then the length is the width times the plastic ratio cubed, or $1.87\rho^3 \mathcal{C}$.

The third occurrence will be discussed in a separate article about the speed of light.

6 Triangles and the double square

Given that $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$, we can rewrite our definition as

$$\vartheta = \frac{\pi}{e} \times \varphi \tag{1}$$

$$= \frac{\pi}{e} \times \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \tag{2}$$

$$= \frac{\pi(1+\sqrt{5})}{2e} \tag{3}$$

$$= \frac{\pi + \pi\sqrt{5}}{2e} \tag{4}$$

$$= \frac{\pi}{2e} + \frac{\pi\sqrt{5}}{2e} \tag{5}$$

The ratio between these two terms is

$$\frac{\pi}{2e} : \frac{\pi\sqrt{5}}{2e} = 1 : \sqrt{5}$$

The two numbers, 1 and $\sqrt{5}$, immediately suggest that Giza favourite, the double square which leads to the golden ratio. That would be based on the back to back double triangle with sides

$$\frac{\pi}{2e} : \frac{\pi}{e} : \frac{\pi\sqrt{5}}{2e}$$

In numbers as lengths, this is

$$0.5779 : 1.1557 : 1.2921$$

Figure 1: Thoth's Constant in triangle and double square form

7 Curiosity related to Khufu's dimensions

Take 1.87 metres, and convert to cubits,

$$1.87 \times \frac{6}{3.1416} = \overline{3.571428}$$

Multiply by Khufu's height

$$\overline{3.571428} \times 280 = 1000$$

The result is exact. Well, at the limit.

Due to $\frac{440}{280} \approx \frac{\pi}{2}$, doing the same operation with the base gives approximately 500π .

$$\overline{3.571428} \times 440 = 1571.428571 \approx 500\pi$$

Bibliography

- [1] Douglas, Ian, *The Beautiful Cubit System*, 2019-06-30. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3263864>.
- [2] I. Douglas, 'The Beautiful System', Zenodo, 2022-02-10. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6121399. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/6121399> (visited on 2022-05-23).
- [3] —, 'Khufu's Coffin', Zenodo, 2021-09-19. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5539862. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/5539862> (visited on 2022-05-12).